

Menopause Rodent Models: Suitability for Cognitive Aging Research

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ABSTRACT

Background: Recently published findings noted that women suffer from Alzheimer disease, a form of neurodegenerative disorder, more often than men, even accounting for the fact that women on average live longer.

Objective: Menopause rodent model may be an invaluable tool for assessing longitudinal effects of hormones and aging, as well as providing access to body tissues especially brain, from which insight into the mechanisms related to cognitive aging and Alzheimer disease can be gleaned.

Method: This review highlights the suitability and limitations of using menopause rodent models for cognitive aging research.

Conclusion: Intact aging and OVX animals mimic natural and surgical menopause, respectively, hence making them suitable menopause models for cognitive aging research after taking into account their limitations.

KEY WORDS

Alzheimer disease, menopause, rodents, intact aging, ovariectomized, accelerated ovarian failure

INTRODUCTION

Menopause is the cessation of menstruation at the end of a woman's reproductive life and, by definition, is the absence of menstruation for a year¹⁾. Natural menopause is the result of loss of ovarian follicular activity due to natural aging^{2,3)}. Another form of menopause is medically-induced menopause. It is the loss of ovarian follicular activity due to surgery, chemotherapy or radiation.

The term perimenopause is defined by the World Health Organization and the North American Menopause Society as two to eight years preceding menopause and one year following final menses^{4,5)}. Menopausal transition stage is divided into early and late phases. It is characterised by irregularity in menstrual cycle with a discrepancy of 7 days or more from the normal cycle. For late menopausal transition, there are 2 or more skipped cycles with an interval of amenorrhea of equal to or more than 60 days⁶⁾. Postmenopausal stage is also divided into two phases, early and late postmenopause. Early postmenopause occurs within 5 - 8 years after cessation of the last menstrual period, while late postmenopause begins after early postmenopause until the remaining of the life span⁷⁾.

MENOPAUSE ANIMAL MODELS

Menopause has been known to cause brain-related symptoms such as depression, anxiety⁸⁾, insomnia⁹⁾ and cognitive deficits¹⁰⁾. Non-human primates experience human-like menopause, but menopause studies in such long-lived mammals are unfeasible¹¹⁾ because of cost and complex variables in lifestyle, history, and time required to study aging systems. Therefore, this review focuses on alternative menopause models using small laboratory animals such as rodents for cognitive aging research. Genetically modified animal models (transgenic and knock-out animals) such as aromatase deficiency and APP23 transgene mouse model¹²⁾, and Follicle Stimulating Hormone receptor knockout (FORKO) mice¹³⁾, however, are beyond the scope of this review.

The ideal menopause model should have similarity to endocrine and neuroendocrine aspects of human ovarian biology, and if possible, the model should have reproductive traits that can be manipulated in the laboratory, that is, by transgenic or natural mutations that result in an accelerated or delayed example of ovarian aging. Rodents have a maximum lifespan of 5 years, their ovaries deteriorate as they age and they can be genetically manipulated, making them a suitable menopause model¹⁴⁾. Table 1 summarizes comparison between human and rodent reproductive senescence.

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Table 1. Comparison between human and rodent reproductive senescence¹⁵⁾

	Human	Rodents
Cycle	Menstrual cycle	Estrus cycle; proestrus, estrus, metestrus, diestrus
Duration per cycle	25-30 days/cycle	4-5 days/cycle
Menstruation	Shed endometrial lining as menstruation	Reabsorbed endometrial lining, no menstruation
Transitional age of reproductive senescence	Experience irregular estrus cycle (estropause) around 9-12 months of age	Experience irregular menstrual cycle (perimenopause) around 47-49 years of age
Reason for menopause	Complete ovarian failure	Dysregulated HPG axis

Table 2. Menopause animal models

Model	Presence of		Estrogen level
	Perimenopause	Postmenopause	
Intact aging	√	√	Low but persistent estrogen level
OVX		√	Low to undetectable estrogen level
AOF	√	√	Low to undetectable estrogen level

There are three main types of menopause animal models; intact aging (natural menopause), surgical menopause or ovariectomized (OVX) and accelerated ovarian failure (AOF)¹⁴⁾. Clinical evidence suggests that the consequences of these models to hormone loss in women may be different as each model produce differential effects and the choice of the model depends on the study objectives. AOF model may offer new insight into the health of women, particularly in determining the critical periods during perimenopause when ovarian hormones can be restored to treat memory and mood disorders as well as other menopausal symptoms most effectively¹⁶⁾. As in women, surgical menopause model exhibit lower memory scores relative to natural menopause model, and greater years post-surgery positively correlate with poorer performance¹⁷⁾. Thus, surgical menopause model may have greater negative consequences for cognitive function compared to natural menopause model. Table 2 summarizes the different menopause animal models.

INTACT AGING MODEL

The main advantage of intact aging model is more similar to human menopause with hormonal fluctuations during the menopause transition similar to that occurring in middle-aged women, hence its suitability to be used as intact model of menopause. However this model lacks a true menopause phase (very low to undetectable estrogen level) as the intact aging rodents model undergo reproductive senescence; a change referred to as estropause i.e. low but persistent estrogen level, and is not a true menopause¹⁸⁾.

The rodents are anovulatory but with very low to undetectable estrogen level, progesterone level may be increased; and unlike humans, mice and rats ovaries retain follicles throughout their lifespan¹⁸⁾. The estrogen level in rats is not reduced to an undetectable level as in mice or humans¹⁹⁾. Rats are also able to retain a larger number of primary follicles and demonstrate a greater decrease in estrogen level than mice during estropause¹⁸⁾.

In human menopause, physiological alterations occur in the hypothalamus-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis as well as demonstrating very low ovarian estrogen and progesterone levels. In the intact aging model, the loss of ovarian functions is precipitated by changes in hormonal and metabolic activities whereby the model may exhibit many features of human menopause. These include nearly undetectable steroid hormones, elevated serum gonadotropins, ovarian morphological aging, and health problems that are associated with menopause, such as decreased bone density and elevated serum cholesterol²⁰⁾. Therefore, the aging model provides insight into the general mechanisms or consequences of menopause, although the basic mechanism responsible for reproductive senescence differs slightly from human menopause¹⁸⁾.

In women, as aging approaches, serum estrogen and progesterone levels decrease due to decreased ovarian follicular reserves. Thus, hormonal loss for natural (nonsurgical) menopause is ultimately due to ovarian follicle depletion. On the contrary, a persistent estrus state in aging rat is due to slightly elevated estrogen level. Chronic anovulation

followed by a persistent diestrus state is characterized by high progesterone level secondary to increased corpora lutea activity. These changes in ovarian hormone release are primarily due to alterations in the HPG axis. Thus, the primary mechanism that ultimately results in reproductive senescence in woman is the ovarian follicle depletion, whereas in rat it is the alteration in the HPG axis²¹⁾.

OVARIECTOMIZED (OVX) MODEL

The OVX model mimics surgically-induced menopause in humans and provides insight into the role of estrogen in measured responses. This model is non-genetically manipulated and is considered an appropriate and accurate model to mimic surgical menopause in human.

However, this model has two major disadvantages. First, OVX model rodents do not model natural, transitional menopause^{22,23)}. In the OVX model, ovarian hormones are removed abruptly while in natural menopause there is a gradual alteration of hormones which start to occur at perimenopause period and changes seen in the transition phase prior to reaching postmenopause²⁴⁾.

Second, in addition to estrogens, OVX depletes many other hormones that likely have important roles in menopause and activation effects on the brain^{18,19,25)}, in particular, the central regulators of estrogens, LH, gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), and FSH^{18,19,25,26)}. Since the ovaries are removed, there is no secretion of androgens by residual ovarian tissue as occurs in natural menopause^{27,28)}.

Apart from OVX, hysterectomy alone or with unilateral OVX has also been shown to have a negative impact on the reproductive hormonal function as well as cognitive integrity²⁹⁾. There are three proposed theories to explain this issue. The first theory is that, during hysterectomy procedures, surgical ligation and transection of the infundibulopelvic ligament (which contains the ovarian branch of the uterine artery), as well as the ligament of the ovary (containing ovarian vasculature), causes ischemia of ovarian tissue leading to loss of primordial follicles³⁰⁾. The second theory is that the indication for the woman to have a hysterectomy (such as fibroids or abnormal uterine bleeding) might have predisposed her to have premature menopause³¹⁾. Finally, the third theory suggests that the uterus is an endocrine organ that secretes paracrine factors that regulate the recruitment of follicles³²⁾, and loss of these factors might lead to premature menopause due to a faster depletion of follicles.

ACCELERATED OVARIAN FAILURE (AOF) MODELS

The intact aging model fails to achieve very low to undetectable estrogen level, and the OVX model lacks a perimenopause phase. A new rodent model of AOF successfully replicates human perimenopause and postmenopause, by manifesting estrous acyclicity, and fluctuating followed by undetectable estrogen level. This allows for the dissociation of the effects of hormone levels from the effects of aging.

There are two classes of ovotoxins that are used to induce AOF; 4-vinylcyclohexene diepoxide (VCD) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons found in cigarette smoke. Of the two, VCD is the better studied³³. VCD acts by selectively accelerating the natural loss of small primordial and primary follicles³⁴ when administered repeatedly to mice and rats³⁵. The exact mechanism by which it acts to initiate atresia is still largely unknown; however, it is believed to accelerate the natural processes of atresia³⁵. Induction of premature ovarian failure is thus possible via depletion of the pool of primordial follicles. The mechanism of action by which VCD acts is thought to be via proapoptotic pathways³⁶.

In a study by Mayer *et al.*³⁷, Fischer-344 rats had significantly reduced numbers of preantral follicles following 30 days administration of VCD at 80 mg/kg/day. Circulating levels of FSH were elevated by 120 days in VCD-treated rats as compared with vehicle animals, although no apparent ultrastructural difference between groups was seen. Furthermore, cyclicity was disrupted in VCD-treated rats by 360 days³⁷. Experiments in mice yielded similar results: VCD-treated mice exhibited elevated levels of circulating FSH and reduced estradiol at an age where control hormone levels were still normal³⁸. In addition, VCD-treated mice display androgen level similar to postmenopausal hyperandrogenic women³⁹.

Combined, these data demonstrate that the accelerated time frame of the onset of ovarian senescence in VCD-treated mice supports its use as a menopause model, particularly of premature menopause. Since this model requires a longer period to establish disruption to the estrus cycle, it is deemed more suitable to be used in studies that investigate apoptosis-regulated pathways leading to ovarian depletion and menopause, whether normal or premature.

However, this model has its disadvantages. There are well-documented toxic and/or carcinogenic effects of VCD compound on other organ systems such as lung, and liver, apart from ovaries. These effects, however, depend on the dose and duration of exposure⁴⁰. Additionally, the chemico-physical properties of VCD compound such as small molecular mass of 108.18 g/mol, cyclohexene structure, and preferential distribution of this compound into lipid suggest the potential of its accumulation in the brain over the period of exposure to induce follicular atresia³³. For this reason, it is an unsuitable menopause animal model for Alzheimer disease.

CONCLUSION

Although AOF successfully replicates human perimenopause and postmenopause, it is unsuitable for cognitive aging research because of its potential brain toxicity. Intact aging and OVX animals mimic natural and surgical menopause, respectively, hence making them suitable menopause models for cognitive aging research after taking into account their limitations.

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